

Cooperation Between Selawi Bambu Creative Center (SBCC) Mekarsari Village, Selawi District, Garut Regency And President Penyet Chicken Restaurant In Improving Cooperation Bambu Cooperation With Singapore In 2022-2023

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received July 18, 2025

Revised July 20, 2025

Accepted August 21, 2025

Available online Agustus 23, 2025

Keywords:

Bamboo Crafts, Export Cooperation, Penyet President Chicken Restaurant & Singapore

Keywords:

Kerajinan Bambu .Kerjasama Ekspor, Restoran Ayam Penyet President & Singapura

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to examine the potential for cooperation in exporting bamboo crafts from Mekarsari Village, Selawi District, Garut Regency to Singapore. Mekarsari Village is known as a production center for unique and high quality bamboo crafts. Factors such as production sustainability, design innovation, and economic sustainability in Mekarsari Village are the focus of this research. The research methods used are interviews with bamboo craft industry players, surveys to assess production sustainability, and market analysis to evaluate export potential to chicken restaurants. President in Singapore. International Relations Explained Through Bilateral Cooperation Between Mekarsari Village and Export Partners of President's Chicken Restaurant in Singapore. This research article shows that Mekarsari Village has great potential to increase exports of bamboo crafts to President Chicken Restaurant in Singapore. Factors such as well managed production sustainability, design innovation that combines traditional and modern, and economic sustainability can be the main attraction for the international market. Strong Bilateral Cooperation Between Local Government, Industry Players, and

Export Partners of the President's Chicken Restaurant in Singapore is the Key to Success in Developing the Export Market for Mekarsari Village Bamboo Craft Products. This research makes a positive contribution to local economic development and strengthens international relations between Mekarsari Village and Singapore and various other countries.

ABSTRACT

Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk mengkaji potensi kerjasama ekspor kerajinan bambu dari desa mekarsari, kecamatan selawi, kabupaten garut ke singapura .desa mekarsari dikenal sebagai sentra produksi kerajinan bambu yang unik dan berkualitas tinggi. Faktor-faktor seperti keberlanjutan produksi, inovasi desain, dan keberlanjutan ekonomi di desa mekarsari menjadi fokus penelitian ini. metode penelitian yang digunakan adalah wawancara dengan pelaku industri kerajinan bambu, survei untuk menilai keberlanjutan produksi, dan analisis pasar untuk mengevaluasi potensi ekspor ke ke restoran ayam president di singapura . Hubungan internasional dijelaskan melalui kerjasama bilateral antara desa mekarsari dan mitra ekspor restoran ayam president di singapura. Artikel penelitian ini menunjukkan bahwa desa mekarsari memiliki potensi besar untuk meningkatkan ekspor kerajinan bambu ke restoran ayam president di singapura. Faktor-faktor seperti keberlanjutan produksi yang dikelola dengan baik, inovasi desain yang memadukan tradisional dan modern, serta keberlanjutan ekonomi dapat menjadi daya tarik utama bagi pasar internasional. Kerjasama bilateral yang kuat antara pemerintah lokal, pelaku industri, dan mitra ekspor restoran ayam president di singapura menjadi kunci keberhasilan dalam mengembangkan pasar ekspor untuk produk kerajinan bambu desa mekarsari. Penelitian ini memberikan kontribusi positif terhadap pengembangan ekonomi lokal dan memperkuat hubungan internasional antara desa mekarsari dan singapura serta berbagai negara lainnya .

INTRODUCTION

The term "international relations" or "IR" can be defined as a study that compares and contrasts the activities and responsibilities of national and non-national actors, as well as international organizations, non-national organizations, and multinational corporations.

One indicator of activities within international relations is the interaction between national or international organizations. Sorensen (2013) also notes that countries around the world are increasingly

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strengthening their position of worldwide interdependence, which is increasingly evident, and the focus is on efforts to improve the welfare of a nation based on the principles of mutual trust, respect, and appreciation. Cooperation in economic, political, educational, business, and security sectors can be found in both bilateral and multilateral agreements. Zulkifli (2012) notes that to improve bilateral and multilateral relations between countries, cooperation is essential, especially in international trade. Currently, all countries around the world are competing to sell domestically produced processed and industrial products and export them to other countries. Countries only seek profit and increase their economic income. International trade is a crucial aspect of the economies of countries around the world. With international trade, economies become interconnected, creating mutually influential economic relationships between countries, and the movement of goods and services shapes trade between countries. International trade is trade conducted by residents of one country with residents of another country based on mutual agreement. The populations in question can be individuals, between individuals, between individuals and the government of a country, or between the government of one country and the government of another country. Although international trade has existed for thousands of years, its impact on economic, social, and political interests has only been felt in the last few centuries. International trade also facilitates industrialization, advances in transportation, globalization, and the presence of multinational corporations.

International trade is a source of income for the Indonesian economy. International trade has a significant impact on a country's economic growth because all countries compete in the international market. One of the benefits of international trade is that it allows a country to specialize in the production of low-cost goods and services, both in terms of materials and production methods. However, the real benefits of international trade come in the form of increased income, foreign exchange reserves, capital transfers, and employment opportunities. Mekarsari Village, located in South Garut, is home to numerous craft and food processing industries, particularly bamboo crafts. The bamboo craft industry in Mekarsari can help improve the local economy and create jobs, especially for young people in the area.

Bamboo craft production in Mekarsari has the potential to reach wider international markets, such as Europe and Asia, particularly Singapore, known as one of the world's economic centers. However, limited knowledge and resources related to exports are major obstacles. By accessing international markets, the income of the Mekarsari Village community is expected to increase, and they will be able to sell their products at more profitable prices. This export project is expected to create new jobs, both in production and logistics, thereby reducing the unemployment rate.

The collaboration between Mekar Bambu Craft from Mekar Sari Village and a chicken restaurant owned by a well-known businessman has had a tremendous positive impact on the village's economy and development. By supplying bamboo furniture, particularly chandeliers, to several restaurant chains throughout Singapore, Mekar Bambu Craft has successfully established itself as a major player in the bamboo craft industry. This success is reflected not only in the positive reception from restaurant customers who appreciate the uniqueness and beauty of the bamboo chandeliers, but also in the significant economic impact on Mekar Sari Village. By exporting bamboo craft products to Singapore, Mekar Bambu Craft has been able to substantially increase the village's income. The culmination of this collaboration is monthly sales reaching an extraordinary figure of 100 million rupiah. This income not only provides a significant economic contribution to the artisans and residents of Mekar Sari Village, but also creates new jobs and empowers local communities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

International Relations Review

International Relations Perwita & Yani (2005:1) state that international relations are highly dynamic, evolving in line with the development of human social life and influenced by changes in environmental (natural) conditions. Early in its development, a number of experts argued that international relations encompassed all relations between states. Quoting Schwarzenberger, international relations is a branch of sociology that specifically studies international society (sociology of international relations).

Therefore, international relations, in its general sense, encompasses not only political elements but also economic, social, cultural, defense, and other aspects, such as population movement (immigration and emigration), tourism, the Olympics (sports), or cultural exchange. Currently, international relations is the youngest and most rapidly developing branch or discipline of science. International relations is a form of interaction between actors or members of one society and other actors or members of another society.

The emergence of international relations is a necessity due to the interdependence and increasing complexity of human life in the international community, making it impossible for any country to close

itself off from the outside world (Perwita & Yani, 2005). According to T. May Rudy (1986:3) in his book "International Administration and Organization," various approaches can be used to study international relations, namely: "Interdisciplinary studies mean that this science can use various theories, concepts, and approaches from other fields in developing its studies. Concerning international aspects (relationships/interactions that cross national borders), this is the field of international relations, with potential links to economics, law, communications, politics, and other areas. Likewise, to study international relations, concepts from sociology, psychology, and even mathematics (probability concepts) can be borrowed and applied to the study of international relations."

International Cooperation

Cooperation can grow when individuals or parties involved have a common goal to achieve mutual well-being or to fulfill their self-interest. The extent to which one person or party perceives that others will collaborate in a mutually beneficial manner is key to cooperative action. In cooperation theory, the key issue centers on the fulfillment of self-interest. Cooperation becomes more beneficial when mutually beneficial outcomes can be achieved through cooperation, rather than through individual efforts or competition between parties. By working together, individuals or parties involved can achieve more optimal and efficient results, while also utilizing their respective resources and expertise. Cooperation is an important foundation in international relations and business because it can create win-win solutions, or solutions that benefit all parties involved (Dougherty & Pfaltzgraff, 1997: 419).

International Trade

According to Christianto (2013), the simple definition of international trade, according to the economics dictionary, is trade that takes place between two or more countries. Foreign trade is a vital element in a country's economy. It not only plays a role in export-oriented national development, but also aims to find markets in other countries for domestic products and provide capital goods to support domestic industrial growth. International trade begins with the exchange of labor for goods and services. The basis of this trade is the transaction of goods and services between two or more countries with the goal of making a profit. International trade occurs when there is supply and demand in the global market.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research model used as the basis for this study's analysis is a qualitative method. Qualitative research methods aim to explain the cause and effect of events that occur realistically so that the analysis results can provide a clear picture of the situation (Fadli, 2021). This study used a qualitative method with a focus on analyzing the problem of collaboration between the Selawi Bambu Creative Center (SBCC) Association and the President Ayam Penyet Restaurant in improving bamboo crafts in Mekarsari Village, Selawi District, Selawi Regency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the context of international relations, liberalism theory emphasizes the importance of cooperation between actors, both state and non-state, to achieve mutual benefits. The bamboo craft export collaboration between MSMEs in Mekarsari Village and the President Ayam Penyet Restaurant reflects this principle, where both parties strive to create a mutually beneficial relationship. Through exports, MSMEs can increase revenue and expand their market, while the restaurant obtains quality products to support its business. International trade theories, such as the theory of comparative advantage, are also relevant in explaining this collaboration. Comparative advantage suggests that a country or region should produce goods at a relatively lower cost than other countries. Mekarsari Village has an advantage in bamboo crafts due to the availability of local raw materials and traditional craftsmanship. By leveraging this advantage, exporting products to international markets, such as in the collaboration with the President Ayam Penyet Restaurant, can provide added value to the local economy. However, realism theory in international relations can also be used to understand the challenges of this collaboration. Realism emphasizes that each actor in the international system acts in its own self-interest. Barriers such as lack of communication, the absence of a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU), and price competition reflect the conflicting interests between MSMEs and restaurants. Therefore, proposed solutions, such as establishing a formal cooperation agreement and strengthening communication, aim to reduce tensions and build trust.

Using this approach, bamboo craft export cooperation can be seen as a combination of efforts to maximize mutual benefits (liberalism), utilize comparative advantages (international trade theory), and overcome obstacles arising from each party's interests (realism). Strategic steps such as product diversification, global market expansion, and product quality improvement reflect efforts to realize sustainable economic benefits while strengthening the bargaining position of local actors in the international market. In implementing bamboo craft export cooperation, the role of international relations theories such as constructivism can also be analyzed. Constructivism focuses on the importance of values,

norms, and identities in shaping interactions between actors. In this context, bamboo crafts are not merely an economic commodity but also reflect the local cultural values and identity of the Mekarsari Village community. Exporting these products not only provides financial benefits but also introduces Indonesia's rich culture to the global market, thereby helping to create a positive image of the country internationally. However, emerging challenges, such as changes in international trade regulations or policies, can also be explained through an institutionalist approach to international relations.

Institutionalism recognizes the importance of international institutions and regulations in facilitating cooperation. To overcome such obstacles, closer collaboration between MSMEs, the government, and international organizations is needed to ensure that regulations do not hinder exports but instead support the growth of local businesses.

By integrating international relations and international trade theories into the analysis of bamboo craft export cooperation, it is clear that the success of this collaboration depends not only on economic aspects but also on strengthening communication, cultural values, and managing the dynamics of relationships between actors. This comprehensive approach will help MSMEs and related parties overcome obstacles, maximize export potential, and increase the economic contribution of bamboo crafts to local and national development.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis and discussion, it can be concluded that the bamboo craft export collaboration between MSMEs in Mekarsari Village and the Ayam President Restaurant has significant potential to boost the local economy. This is reflected in the positive impacts that artisans can experience, such as a significant increase in income and the opening of new market opportunities. Bamboo crafts serve not only as an economic commodity but also as a means of introducing local Indonesian culture to the global market. Thus, bamboo craft exports contribute to economic growth, both at the individual artisan level and for the Mekarsari Village community as a whole.

However, in its implementation, there are obstacles that can disrupt the smooth running of this export collaboration. Some of the main obstacles identified include a lack of effective communication between the parties involved, the absence of a formal agreement such as a Memorandum of Understanding (MOU), and a decline in export volume, which can impact the stability of product supply. Inconsistent product quality and limited production capacity of MSMEs are other obstacles that must be overcome. To overcome these obstacles, several efforts can be undertaken, such as improving communication and coordination between relevant parties, drafting clear and formal cooperation agreements, and improving product quality through innovation and increased production capacity. Furthermore, product diversification and market expansion can also open up new and broader opportunities for MSMEs, reducing their dependence on a single business partner.

SUGGESTION

Suggestions for Enhancing the Government's Role in Supporting Bamboo Craft MSME Exports in Mekarsari Village. The government plays a crucial role in strengthening bamboo craft MSME exports in Mekarsari Village. **Open and Regular Communication:** Maintaining open channels of communication between both parties is crucial. Regular meetings or discussion sessions can help clarify expectations, resolve issues quickly, and strengthen collaborative relationships. **Product Quality Monitoring:** The Creative Bambu Center Association needs to ensure that the bamboo craft products produced meet the quality standards expected by Ayam President Restaurant. Improving product quality can reduce the risk of customer dissatisfaction and strengthen brand reputation. **Flexibility in Scheduling and Delivery:** Ayam President Restaurant and the Creative Bambu Center Association need to work together to arrange production and delivery schedules that align with needs and demand.

Scheduling flexibility can help avoid delivery delays and meet established deadlines. **Drafting a Flexible Agreement:** The MOU should be designed flexibly to accommodate potential changes in the collaboration. Clauses regarding price adjustments, product returns, or changes in specifications should be carefully considered to avoid future conflicts. **Continuous Evaluation and Improvement:** Both parties should periodically evaluate their collaboration. Identify areas for improvement and commit to continuously enhancing the performance and efficiency of the collaboration. By adopting these suggestions, the Creative Bambu Center Association and President Chicken Restaurant can strengthen their collaborative relationship in the export of bamboo craft products, overcome potential obstacles, and achieve long-term mutual success.

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